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Creative Cultural Economy in the Era of COVID-19: An Analysis of Handicrafts from India and South Korea

Mr. Shahid Jamal* and Prof. Anjan Sen**

[The entire world is facing the biggest challenge after World War II as coronavirus pandemic has affected every country of the world. In such unusual circumstance, informal sector of economy is affected the most due to its minimal support from government unlike formal sector. Creative cultural economy is among the first to shut down in response to COVID-19 pandemic and is among the last to reopen. The artisans faced very painful hardship because they are left with no financial support to earn their livelihood during the pandemic. The government of all countries, whether be India or South Korea imposed lockdown throughout to contain spread of coronavirus. During lockdown, demand for handicraft products have declined exponentially as everyone stays focused on basic goods whereas handicrafts are discrete products. The objective of study is to identify and analyse level of challenges faced by handicraft economy of India and South Korea during COVID-19 pandemic. After analysis, it was concluded that informal sector is the backbone of any economy as it provides maximum employment after agriculture. The government can reduce hardship faced by Artisans during the pandemic through its Artisans oriented policies and schemes.]

The term heritage consists two words in Indian tradition where *dhara* stands for mother earth and *ihara* means identity through time and Varanasi wall hanging is also one of heritage work (Singh et al., 2020). Varanasi is renowned for its excellent wall hanging with exclusive and rare production technique (Mehrotra, 2019). It represents India's creative culture and derived its name wall hanging as used for wall hanging merely (Singh, 2018). It is used to showcase and increase wall's decoration and it develops link between cultural heritage and modernity (Fengfan and Yue, 2017). The community involves three level of hierarchal classification wherein gaddidars occupy top position (Singh, 2021).

The Republic of Korea's traditional embroiders elucidates an ultimate intricate art of handicraft as with each and every stitch symbolizing dedicated Jogakbo artisans required for intangible creative cultural legacy (Mee-yoo, 2016). Artisans prepare more than hundred designs of traditional Jogakbo's products demand in different markets that represents apex of Korean handicrafts in the world (Yang, 2016). South Korea's creative cultural embroidery is association of different products such as Jogakbo shoes, wrapping cloth is locally called as bojagi and women's ensemble (Kim, and Lee, 2011). Bojagi is a Korean traditional cloth with complete phoenix (Kim and Hong, 2009). Artisan's dedication in each thread stitch draws attention of handicraft lovers and are highly impressed with their handicraft products and adored

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their artwork (Park, 2013). It is irony that despite of having infinite qualities, Jogakbo embroidery is very rarely seen due to its antiqueness (Ban, 2006).

History will remember COVID-19 (SARS-CoV-2) as the biggest tragedy of 21st century (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2020). The artisans of handicraft products such as Jogakbo from South Korea and wall hanging from India faced a lot of problems during coronavirus pandemic. Although, both the countries managed to flattened curve of coronavirus within time following three simple steps of test, trace and treat (Dangol and Chitrakar, 2021). India recorded its 1st COVID-19's positive case in Kerala on 27 January 2020 while South Korea on January 20, 2020 (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2020). In India, for containing spread of coronavirus outbreak, the union government imposed complete lockdown while Korean government avoiding economic lockdown across the country as their government respond quickly to pandemic (International Labour Organisation, November 2020). Artisans believe that cultural heritage has the greatest appeal worldwide with aim to globalise creative culture using traditional skills and techniques (Kim, 2016). They are in a constant path to transform their art into a sustainable handicraft economy with appreciated art form even in times of SARS-CoV-2 (Cho, 2016).

Origin through the Pages of Time

The origin of Jogakbo is dating back to centuries that was commonly prepared in entire Republic of Korea and particularly in Cheongju part of Korea (Noh and Lim, 2003). The art of packaging Jogakbo cloths delighted a long history in Korean culture and during period of Joseon dynasty from 1392-1910 it was thrived a lot (Lee and Choi, 2011). Subsequently, Jogakbo embroidery work attained momentum in beginning of 21st century dawn which rediscovered hidden beauty of Korean traditional creative cultural economy (Yang, 2014). Erstwhile, women used to live in patriarchal society and debarred from attaining formal education and focused more on domestic work like embroidery and weaving (Ha, 2003). Later, they prepared wrapping cloths, costumes and beddings for household decoration to earn source of livelihood and area of interest (Park and Lee, 2008). During Joseon dynasty, idea of simplicity and accessibility to common people gained momentum (Chung, 2014). Prior, scraps of leftover fabrics were discarded, are now preserved to make antique handicraft products (Kim and Chae, 2014). These fabrics are joined together to produce Jogakbo products in square, tangent and rectangular shape (Lim and Kwen, 2004).

India's heart lies in village and the village's heart dwell in handicrafts like wall hanging (Singh, 1988). It is being produced since time immemorial and came in light to general public in 2017, when it was given Geographical Indications (GI) tag (Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade, 2021). Erstwhile, jute was used to prepare wall hanging, but with changing time and consumers demand wool is also being used widely together with jute (Fengfan and Yue, 2017). The role of nakshband is vital in wall hanging because they used to prepare designs for wall hanging which later artisans carve in their final wall hanging framework (Geographical Indications Journal, 2020). Earlier, female artisans were allowed widely to prepare wall hanging, but in current scenario it is very rare to find any female artisans involved in wall hanging (Arora, 2018). Around 1950s, there were several clusters where wall hangings were used to

prepare such as Baburi, Sahabgunj, Chittanpura and Konia (Geographical Indications Journal, 2014). The number of these clusters have reduced to Baburi and Chittanpura in the beginning of 21st century and today it is restricted to Baburi only (Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade, 2021).

Study Area

Varanasi erstwhile renowned as Banaras and got India's 1st handicraft mega cluster in 2016 (Singh, 2016). Varanasi since time immemorial famous as premier hub for handicraft products of the country (Ministry of Textiles, 2021). Some of the most renowned handicraft products of Varanasi includes Banaras brocades and sarees and Varanasi wall hanging (Sharma, 2019: Fig. 1). Deendayal Hastkala Sankul (DHS) is an imperative step in this direction which is embedded with modern facility of government of India to support handicraft sector (Deendayal Hastkala Sankul, 2018).

Fig. 1 Prepared by Author, 2021 (Adopted from ARC GIS 10.5, 2021)

Cheongju

Cheongju is situated in northern Chungcheong province and organising Cheongju international craft biennale since 1999 (He-suk, 2020: Fig. 2). Cheongju has two branch that are designated as craft city; one is renowned as artistic crafts emerged form cultural heritage and second is living craft originated from efforts of local community (Huh et al., 2020). Jogakbo is one of the Artistic and living crafts that has a place for craft distinctiveness. As a result, mega craft regeneration projects developed in the region to provide livelihood (Jeong and Ban, 2020). The dominated rich cultural heritage of Cheongju are fabricated into intangible cultural and historical heritage which is spread over an area of 153 sq. km with total population of 6.4 lakh (Yim et a., 2015).

Fig. 2 Prepared by Author, 2021 (Adopted from ARC GIS 10.5, 2021)

Research Objective

Identify and analyse level of challenges faced by handicraft economy of India and South Korea during COVID-19 pandemic.

Database and Research Methodology

The research creates awareness of need to invest in creativity, protection and fair analysis of grass root reality in any designated region. The study is an attempt to systematize and collect qualitative and quantitative information about creative culture economy in light of COVID-19 pandemic impact on handicraft sector of India and Republic of Korea. Pandemic caused a great social and economic disruption as human

beings didn't experience such phenomenon over past 100 year. It is difficult to relate and combine all complexities in one meta study.

The study majorly based on primary survey followed secondary data. Some of the secondary data sources referred includes census of India, district census handbook, Journal of Korean Society of Costume, Korea.net, Food and Agriculture Organisation. Further referred Korean Cultural Centre, Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, International Labour Organisation and annual conference proceedings for comprehensive analysis. Policymakers, scholars and renowned institutions have gathered all important information at various stages, gave grass root reality through livelihood aspects during COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, household survey was conducted between 2019-2021 at wall hanging cluster such as Baburi, India. Total 50 wall hangings artisans were surveyed at Baburi in Uttar Pradesh, India as it is qualitative research work. In case of Jogakbo: Korean patchwork, secondary data was analysed and no primary survey was conducted which was not possible during coronavirus era. Descriptive and empirical methods were used to get detailed and desired outcome. Software such as Arc GIS 10.5 and MS-Office were applied to satisfactorily represent primary survey and secondary data.

Major Findings

COVID-19 pandemic has hit all sectors of economy across the globe and handicraft's creative cultural economy of India and South Korea is not an exception to it. The creative culture has several attributes like population, ethics, gender, language, race, class, government, religion, economy and many more. Economy is one of crucial attributes of creative culture based on place making, which exists together with multiple attributes. The study belongs to handicraft sectors of economy with special focus on artisans from India: Wall Hanging and South Korea: Jogakbo. Some of their significant aspects are discussed below.

a. Uniqueness of Handicrafts

Jogakbo renowned as Korean hand embroidery and patchwork that requires antique skills than any other Korean embroidery (Fig. 3). Women traditionally dominate Jogakbo patchwork as their embroidery is unparalleled to entire traditional handicraft work across the world. Every single stitch capture artisan's devotion and labour as their craftsmanship is making Korean cultural heritage embroidery alive and presenting a unique gift to all. Artisan's continuous dedication and hard work are sole purpose in preserving Korean creative cultural economy and disseminate it to outside world. Handicrafts is a crucial part of religion and daily life of people living in rural areas mainly.

Fig. 3 Jogakbo: Traditional Korean Patchwork (Korean Tourism Organisation, 2019)

Modern artistic consciousness is clubbed and interwoven in development and innovation of creative culture and aesthetic beauty. Although, significance of women is minimal in wall hanging, but it can't be ignored as they perform all auxiliary work related to cleaning of jute and sometimes involved in dyeing. Varanasi wall hanging prepared in classical style and is an antique product of India (Fig. 4). It is prepared creatively in round, square and rectangular shape.

Fig. 4 Jute Wall Hanging (Primary Survey, 2021)

Although, in the current scenario of spinning machines and wide scale industrialism manufacture, it is hard to marvel that unique pattern of animals and flowers fabricated in ceremonial clothing products. It includes bridal gown and silky wall hangings is still exceptional.

b. Psychology of Artisans

Psychology is based on optimistic expectation of future requirement in an induced area. Jogakbo is traditionally used to prepare domestic packaging cloths from discarded fabrics which is locally renowned as bojagi. It is presented as gift to express best wishes, love, affection and blessing to recipient with good luck in their future life. The embroidery patchwork presented to several famous personalities over years like Prime Minister of India: Narendra Modi, Christine Lagarde and Pope Francis during

their visit to Republic of Korea (Fig. 3). It is inherited from spirit of women artisans: happiness and grief of people and interwoven with spirit of integrity. When artisan's surroundings are calm, then they can hear voice of thread and needle piercing the cloth. It is not restricted to scarves and used to produce a wide range of handicraft products including blankets, shawls, shocks, pillow cover and hats. The pinwheel pattern of Jogakbo elucidates people's life that proceed easily and smoothly like dhramachakra parivartana. Applying it to modern world design, designates creative Korean culture motifs that have potential to achieve status of international motifs.

Wall Hanging's manufacturing time depends on efficiency of artisans, size and designs that generally varies from 4 to 5 days and in some cases from 1 to 1.5 months. It is still admired among handicraft and textile lovers because of its antiques hue matching and scenery pattern (Fig. 5). It falls under category of folk art product and its creative cultural heritage is explored. Artisans combine jacquard and several patterns with different jute colour to give distinct appearance. It is clear cut contrast of traditional cultural art with modernity that further enunciates a large, exquisite and rare features of jacquard handloom to match demand and taste of today's customers. The production process starts with colouring and dyeing of jute and wool in different colours with peculiarity of different pieces of products. They used to colour jute and wool in pigment level from 1 to 10 into develop different shades that gives fabulous outlook.

Fig. 5 Artisan Engaged in Wall Hanging's Weaving during COVID-19 (Primary Survey, 2021)

c. Handicraft of Harmony

The creative cultural heritage and art will always be remembered for their successful impression on human civilization. Jogakbo is composed of one type scrap fabric like silk, ramie, which is a plant fibre and has gleaming appearance, paper and cotton. It echoes antiqueness of rich intangible cultural heritage of Cheongju aesthetic beauty. A triple sewn technique is practiced where scarp fabrics are stitched together that is renowned as gekki. Gekki with flat layer in a sealed pattern provides Jogakbo its unique windowpane look. Jogakbo patches are joined together into rectangle, square and extended into different irregular and fashionable size until it reaches needed shape. It inculcates multiple colour composition in light of current demand in modern competitive market (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6 ASEAN Summit: Leaders are wearing Jagakbo Scarves (Adopted from Korea.net. 2015)

Handicrafts are renowned as an antique value added products. It is little difficult to differentiate between craft and handicraft as both are prepared manually whereas handicraft is a part of craft. Artisans are involved in this handicraft from generations and have excelled in art of wall hanging preparation after their continuous endeavour in learning. Among all, scenery pattern is the most famous one and has a lot of demand in metropolitan cities of India and abroad.

d. Impact of COVID-19 on Handicraft

Interconnection between human and environment regarded as power relationship. The relationship between them has worsed over past few years, despite rigorous human efforts to maintain it in its natural form and COVID-19 pandemic is one such examples. The pandemic has affected each and every corner of the earth that unleashed economic earthquake and didn't affect to all in a same manner. Perhaps, it has beaten global financial crisis of 2008-2009 and even worse than the great economic depression of 1930s. Micro Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) that includes handicraft sector is more vulnerable to repercussions of pandemic. Lockdown made evident significance of creative cultural economy for people during pandemic. India followed more stringent lockdown to contain the spread of coronavirus whereas South Korea followed less stringent lockdown for containment of coronavirus. It is unfortunate that pandemic brought societal, political, psychological, economical changes and synthetically shape out handicraft economy of India and South Korea.

Along with tourism, creative cultural sector are the hardest hit during global crisis as a result, an abrupt decline in revenue earned from these sectors. It leads to lower wages for workers or artisans involved therein. The adverse effect of pandemic on distribution channels will hamper their production in months or in years to come. Artisans were compelled to shut down their heritage work and find out some other work to earn their livelihood due to absence of responsive support during pandemic (Fig. 7). Some artisans shifted to agriculture wherein stress was already witnessed while other absorbed in construction activities at lower wages than daily farmers and workers respectively. Apart from economic loss, it has impacted psychological health of people because it is a global health crisis as during lockdown they were locked in their home without work.

In many regions and clusters specialisation in creative cultural economy is evolving to parallel the current expectations. It is being used to tackle economic challenges like competition to capture more market shares from new angles like art creation and making it more resilience to common cause. The temporary support in terms of schemes and policies were ill adopted and ill proven during pandemic, when these were needed utmost.

Fig. 7 Economic Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic (Prepared by Author, 2021)

It has two objectives that is it must have vision and leading to a higher goal of achievement. Whatever may be crisis or depth of lake, stream and river and whatever may be condition of water, the lily flower always comes out of it and blossoms. In this regard, artisans have definite determination to showcase their products to the world which is impossible to achieve, then they will definitely succeed. They have gone to several miserable circumstances where nature has created hurdles and have solved with their power of perseverance. Although, the crisis has paved a way for development of new mask and sanitiser industry in Micro Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). Many artisans diverted to these small industries as it has more scope to flourish in time to come than their traditional handicrafts.

Way Forward

Artisans involved in Jogakbo embroidery and wall hanging are renowned as cultural human assets to the nations. Multiple steps such as exhibition, convention and fairs are organised to highlight importance of their intangible heritage and creative embroidery, some of them are discussed below.

1. Cultural and Economic Dimension

The practice of producing Jogakbo will activate more diverse design. The inheriting Korean cultural assets are putting impression of modern mark on cultural heritage to characterise country's 5 basic colour such as blue, red, yellow, white and black (Fig. 8). These 5 colours are referred as colour that created entire universe. The embroidering requires tough time for gradation of immense designs, but trained artisans even enjoyed

entire process of tough time. Art is described as premium section of handicraft market wherein consumers belong to high income group mostly purchase these products.

Fig. 8 Five Colours Created the Universe (Adopted from Kim and Lee, 2011 and Prepared by Author, 2021)

Generally, artistic handicraft products are quite costly than machinery products, still some consumers have distinct feeling to buy handicraft products over machinery one. There is a hierarchy in wall hanging that starts from artisans or weavers and ends with exporter or export (Fig. 9). Weavers get ₹ 50 as their wage for wall hanging's preparation and same wall hanging will become ₹ 80 when it reaches in girastas hands. Further, same wall hanging will attain price of ₹ 150 when it reaches to gaddidars and its price will become more than ₹ 500 when it exports in global markets. This is economical level of wall hanging where original price is just ₹ 50 and when it reaches to end users, then it becomes ₹ 500.

Fig. 9 Price Rising in Wall Hanging from One Stage to Next (Primary Survey, 2020)

The artisans continue embroidery work for long time. They continue to spread their cultural heritage work as long as their legs are working properly. They are working as the hardest battle in handicraft history to pave way for young artists to come and join their traditional handicraft work. In the era of artificial intelligence and 5th generation technology, it is quite hard to imagine those devoting days for manufacturing of Jogakbo.

2. Creative Cultural Growth

Culture is supposed to grow through level of constrains to creativity and evolution from complex towards simpler one (Fig. 10). Gradual and steady decline in wall hangings were seen in early 21st century as respective textile ministry is no longer patronising these products like before (Fig. 11). Although, wall hanging was given Geographical Indications (GI) status in 2017 to boost its demands, catering duplication of products and encourage younger artisans to join such a rich creative culture. GI status was a positive step in revitalising ancestral cultural heritage of India. Handicraft sector has a great social, economic and cultural impact across India as it is the second largest employment generator. The sector is continuously providing abundant economic opportunities and scope to bring societal change for all.

Fig. 10 Elements of Creative Cultural Growth (Prepared by Author, 2020)

Jogakbo is a colourful wrapping cloth which is a type of bojagi: Korean traditional cloth that gives a rhythmic affection to their rich cultural growth. Blending creative Jogakbo with fashionable art is artisan's extraordinary skills that they are practicing at a highly advanced level. The patchwork invincibly expresses a sense of belongingness and unity in their creative culture as to dye fabric wherein natural dyes are used which exists in blood of Korean Artisans. Fashion is an art work, used to wear on human physique in different ways wherein role of designers is vital because they represent artistic mode of Jogakbo creativity. Despite of scrap cloths, recyclable materials used as raw material in Jogakbo preparation as these are eco-friendly and not harming to life on land and below water. Jogakbo depicts contrast of different colours combination and monocolour of single tone are classical to Korean clothing history.

Fig. 11 Continuous Decline in Number of Wall Hanging Weavers and their Projection (Prepared by Author, 2021)

2. Opposite Relationship

Human beings essentially entered into relationship with their surroundings environment to make mother earth as their abode in a more plastic manner. Human exists in harmonious relationship with environment in such a way to reduce adverse effect of natural hazards so that it won't take form of disasters. Geographers (human) analyse how human beings utilize available natural resources to maintain carrying capacity of surroundings natural environment. During pandemic, decline in all sectors of economy was registered including handicrafts, but sudden improvement in environmental factors such as soil, air and water quality seen simultaneously (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12 Opposite Relationship between Environment and Economy (Prepared by Author, 2021)

It includes reducing acidity of ocean's water, improvement in water quality of seas, rivers, ponds, lakes and other water bodies on mother earth as human beings didn't interfere during the period. The climate change was managed like air quality index across the globe was seeing a healthy level, although that was for very short period of time. Several health related issues itching, inflammation in lungs was controlled temporarily that didn't happen before. Life on land such as improvement in soil quality due to availability of time to regain their nutrients is important for higher crop production. These factors derive humans' action on natural environment and creates impression on entire human civilization.

4. Role of Government

The crisis can never defeat artisans in any manner in whatever condition as they are master of crisis and they defeat crisis. Whenever, they encounter problem, they give problem to the problem. Artisans always have intention and mission of what they can give to nations rather than what they can take from nations. They strive continuously to serve customers and buyers better and better as social and economic development empowered prosperity of nations.

Jogakbo artisans are so competent and skilled that they have realised their artistry and skills and have find out different ways to cherish it more and more in time to come. In current scenario, they are focusing more on abroad products due to its more demand. Hence, they are globalising their rich intangible creative culture in each and every corner of the earth through international exhibition and fashion shows. Artisan's handicrafts can attain more recognition, acknowledgement and esteem from different parts of the world in near future. Jogakbo artisans are not much dependent on their government for investment in this sector. Promotion and purchasing their handicraft

products like Jogakbo shoes, bojagi and women's ensemble is generating good amount of revenue for them. However, they need more favourable and adequate reception for their cultural heritage products regularly.

Ministry of Textiles plays an important role in promoting Varanasi wall hanging through several platforms such as 'Artisan Speak' that showcase rich handicraft tradition of India. Geographical Indications (GI) is another platform to build and promote awareness about such products and strengthening skills and supply chain of creative cultural products at grassroot level. Deendayal Hastkala Sankul (DHS) foundation was laid down on November 7, 2014 is a craft museum. DHS was completed on September 22, 2017 and Shri Narendra Modi inaugurated in Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh to carry forward intangible cultural heritage of Varanasi's Handicrafts including wall hanging. In 2019, Pravasi Bharti Diwas Convention is a flagship program of the Government of India was held in Varanasi. The convention is an attempt to connect and engage Indian diaspora and to make them understand about rich cultural heritage of Varanasi. Inaugurating Hunar Haat in different parts to preserving traditional handicraft products across India. Eventually, role of Smt. Kamaladevi Chattopadhyay is very important in reviving Handicraft and handloom in India.

Conclusion

It is rare to see existence of such a wide variety of hues handicraft products in Asia. India and South Korea are well preserving one of the finest creative cultures and boosting their informal economy through online platforms during COVID-19 as well. In era of pandemic, we have to hold hands together and follow three simple steps not for yourself, but for greater cause of entire human society on the earth. It includes wearing a face mask properly, strictly follow social distancing of at least 2 yards and focus on face and hand hygiene. From environment to enterprises, science to social service, public administration to cinema, culture to cooperatives and agriculture to arts everyone is playing their role in their best possible capacities. Delivering basic services to the last person of society; the poorest of poor is prime duty not only of government, but also of each and every capable section of society. Accessing economic condition of every nook and corner of both the countries is only possible through participation of masses as growth is life and must move.

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